

THE EDUCATION STAKEHOLDERS' PARTICIPATION IN DIFFERENT SCHOOL-INITIATED ACTIVITIES AS INPUTS FOR AN ENHANCED SCHOOL-BASED MANAGEMENT LEVEL OF PRACTICE OF ALL ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS OF SAN MARIANO DISTRICT

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ABSTRACT

School-Based Management (SBM) fosters collaboration between schools and communities, enabling shared governance to fulfill educational mandates and goals, particularly under the decentralized management framework of the Department of Education (DepEd). However, many schools face challenges in achieving recognition and validation for their SBM level of practice, often due to insufficient stakeholder involvement. This issue is particularly prevalent in the San Mariano I & II Districts, where none of the 42 elementary schools were validated for SBM recognition. Despite implementing various strategies, these schools struggle to secure adequate support from internal and external stakeholders in fulfilling the SBM principles: Leadership and Governance, Curriculum and Learning, Accountability and Continuous Improvement, and Management of Resources. The lack of stakeholder participation hampers the school's ability to meet the required standards for SBM validation, as indicated by the limited means of verification. This study aims to assess the level of stakeholder involvement in school-initiated activities and its correlation with SBM performance. Using documentary analysis and survey methods, the research evaluates participation across key SBM dimensions and explores the relationship between stakeholder engagement and SBM outcomes. The findings will inform strategies to enhance stakeholder collaboration, ultimately improving the SBM level of practice and strengthening shared governance in schools.

Keywords: *School-Based Management, Education Stakeholders, School-Initiated Activities*

INTRODUCTION

School-Based Management (SBM) enables the school and the community of working together, facilitating its mandates, targets, programs, projects and activities through shared governance and responsibilities towards achieving the sustained Department of Education goal – the decentralized management. The shared governance and responsibilities that are supposed to be in-placed and practiced between the school and community, however these sometimes be the underlying issue to some schools of not achieving validation and recognition in the SBM Level of Practice.

More often than not, the school leaders and teachers often experiencing difficulties or struggles in establishing support and cooperation from the school community duly represented by the stakeholders in the different school-initiated activities. This becomes the frontline reason why decentralized management is not practice or why SBM Level of Practice is not validated. Despite of numerous strategies and interventions the school applied in achieving sustained support from stakeholders. As school leader, considering the latter experiences, much interest in studying this plight is being intensified, looking for various means and evidences how great is the contribution of education stakeholders in the improvement of SBM level of practice. More so, this endeavor is not only by initiatives but governed with the Department of education mandates.

Pursuant to the above-stated mandate, the Department of Education (DepEd) issued DepEd Order No. 83, s. 2012 to further strengthen the School-Based Management (SBM) level of practice and re-emphasize the centrality of the learners and the involvement of relevant community basic education service delivery – the internal and external stakeholders. But, this issuance is now on its local transition and waiting for the new SBM policy framework to be issued. Thus, DepEd Memorandum No. 75, s. 2022 *re: Moratorium on the Conduct of Division and Regional SBM Validation Activities* is issued, as transitory provision, from SBM recognition-based validation activities to practice-based provision of field technical assistance to all aspiring schools.

However, only few schools nowadays are able to be on ranked to be validated on SBM Level of Practice due to the numerous factors embedded in its four (4) principles; (1) Leadership and Governance; (2) Curriculum and Learning; (3) Accountability and Continuous Improvement; and, (4) Management of Resources. A manifestation that most education leaders fall behind in establishing collaboration among education stakeholders to encourage maximum participation and involvement in different school-initiated activities as the ultimate requirements in order to achieve this goal.

Among 3,084 schools in Region 2, only 81 public elementary and secondary schools are on lists to be validated on SBM Level of Practice in the year 2020 and 13 of 81 schools are from Schools Division of Isabela.

Of 42 elementary schools comprise San Mariano I & II Districts area of responsibility, none of them is validated in SBM Level of Practice. And more often than not, these schools are not able to achieve recognition on SBM Level of Practice due to

poor education stakeholders' participation in completing means of verifications needed, which can only be accomplished through implementation of different school-initiated activities relevant to SBM matters.

In spite of its widespread implementation, SBM in almost all elementary schools of San Mariano I & II Districts have locally received severe attention in terms of stakeholders' participation and that impacted the SBM process towards achieving validation or recognition in level of practice.

In response to this, this study is an attempt to incorporate a strategy to conceptualize stakeholders' participation in the different school-initiated activities and in SBM Level of Practice using the SBM Self-Assessment Tool to evaluate their significant relationship.

Furthermore, SBM also aims at raising and answering some of the questions about stakeholder participation, where SBM is practice rather than recognize only. This enhance commitment of internal and external stakeholders at all levels to their responsibilities and accountabilities in realizing the education outcomes for children and further promote shared governance between the school and the school community.

Of this situation, considering the co-existence of the identified scenarios to almost all elementary schools of San Mariano I & II Districts served as the main reason why the researcher prompted to undertake this study to evaluate the levels of participation of the internal and external stakeholders to different school-initiated activities as contributory variable to achieve SBM level of practice recognition.

Research Questions

This study aimed to evaluate the level of participation of education stakeholders to different school-initiated activities and the SBM level of Practice of all elementary schools in San Mariano I & II Districts, SY 2021-2022.

Specifically, this undertaking answered the following questions:

1. What is the level of participation of education stakeholders to different school-initiated-activities in all elementary schools in San Mariano Districts as perceived by internal and external stakeholders, in-terms of:
 - a. Leadership and Governance
 - b. Curriculum and Learning
 - c. Accountability and Continuous Improvement
 - d. Management of Resources

2. Is there a significant difference in the level of participation of education stakeholders to different school-initiated activities as perceived by the Internal and External Stakeholders?

3. What is the SBM Level of Practice of all elementary schools in San Mariano I & II Districts in-terms of SBM Self-Assessment using the Revised SBM Self-Assessment Tool in-terms of:
 - a. Leadership and Governance
 - b. Curriculum and Learning
 - c. Accountability and Continuous Improvement
 - d. Management of Resources

4. Is there a significance difference of SBM Level of Practice of Central, Non-Central and Integrated Schools?

5. Is there a significant relationship between the level of participation of education stakeholders to the SBM level of practice of all elementary schools in San Mariano I & II Districts?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The researcher utilized the descriptive-correlational research design to properly describe and determine the level of participation of education stakeholders to different school-initiated activities and its relationship to SBM level of practice of the respondents - all elementary schools in San Mariano I & II Districts, SY 2021-2022.

Descriptive correlational design was used in this research study because it aimed to provide statistical descriptions of independent variable referred to as the level of participation of education stakeholders to different school-initiated activities as well as to establish the significant relationship between dependent variable, the SBM level of practice of all elementary schools in San Mariano I & II Districts.

Locale of the Study

The locale for this study is within the Municipality of San Mariano, Isabela. It is a 1st class municipality in the province of Isabela, Philippines. According to the 2020 census, it has a population of 60,124 people. It is also a suburb of neighboring Ilagan, the provincial capital. San Mariano has a total land area of 146,950 hectares (363,100 acres). It constitutes 13.78 percent of the total land area of the province, and is the province's largest and the country's third largest municipality.

The municipality lies in the eastern part of the province of Isabela. It is bounded on the north by the Ilagan, on the east by Palanan, on the south by San Guillermo and on the west by Benito Soliven. It is approximately 404 kilometres (251 mi) from Metro Manila and 46 kilometres (29 mi) from Ilagan, the provincial capital.

Today, San Mariano is continuously being developed, road constructions and other infrastructure project are already being implemented.

Precisely, this study was conducted at the Department of Education, Schools Division of Isabela, specifically all elementary schools under the jurisdiction of San Mariano I & II Districts.

Selection and Description of Respondents

The main source of data for this study were the school heads and the SBM coordinators, and other education stakeholders particularly in all elementary schools in San Mariano I & II Districts using universal sampling since the number of respondents is only few. The other education stakeholders were the School PTA President, Teacher’s Association, SGC Officers, Brgy. Captain, Civic Religious and Kagawad Committee on education. The number of respondents per school was reflected in table 1.

Table 1
Frequency Distribution of Respondents by School

School type	School	Internal Stakeholders					External Stakeholders		
		School Heads	SBM Coordinators	SPTA President	Teachers' Association	SGC Officers	Brgy. Captain	Civic Religious	Kagawad (Committee on Education)
A. San Mariano I District									
Central	San Mariano II Central Integrated School	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1
Non-Central	Alibadabad Elementary School	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1
	Binatug Elementary School	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1
	Casala Elementary School	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1
	Cataguing Elementary School	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1
	Dibuluan Elementary School	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1
	Dipusu Elementary School	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1
	Disulap Elementary School	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1
	Disusuan Elementary School	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1
	Gangalan Elementary School	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1

	Libertad Elementary School	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1
	Luzcon Elementary School	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1
	Malaya Elementary School	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1
	San Pedro Elementary School	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1
	Villa Ancheta Elementary School	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1
Integrated	Del Pilar Integrated School	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1
	Marannao Integrated School	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1
	Panninan Integrated School	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1
	San Isidro Integrated School	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1
	San Jose Integrated School	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1
	Villa Miranda Integrated School	1	1	1	5	1	1	1	1
	Total	21	21	21	105	21	21	21	21

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher forwarded a letter to the Schools Division Superintendent of Schools Division of Isabela thru channels asking permission to float the writer's questionnaire to the identified respondents of the study. After approval, the researcher presented it to the District Supervisor and requested a schedule to meet all school heads and SBM coordinators in the district office. This allowed her to float the questionnaire personally and to explain to them the intent of the study. The researcher personally collected the accomplished questionnaire to ensure 100 percent retrieval.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The collected data were checked for consistency, accuracy and completeness, and then were coded and organized. These were processed and analyzed through the guidance of an expert statistician.

In this study, the following statistical tools were used to treat, analyze and interpret the results:

Weighted Mean. This statistical tool was used to answer sub-problem numbers 1 and 3.

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). This test was used to determine the significant difference in the level of participation within internal and external stakeholders to the different school-initiated activities and the SBM level of practice of the three types of school-respondents.

Independent t-test. This statistical tool was used to determine the significant difference in the level of participation of internal and external stakeholders to different school-initiated activities.

Pearson Product Moment Correlation (Pearson r) and Regression Analysis. These statistical tool was used to answer sub-problem number 5 at five percent level of significance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Level of Participation of Education Stakeholders to Different School-Initiated-Activities

a. Internal Stakeholders

1. Leadership and Governance

Table 2

Level of Participation of Internal Stakeholders to Different School-Initiated-Activities in All Elementary schools in San Mariano Districts in Terms of Leadership and Governance

Leadership and Governance	Internal Stakeholders										Average Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
	School Heads		SBM Coordinators		Teachers' Association		PTA President		SPG Officers			
	WM	QD	WM	QD	WM	QD	WM	QD	WM	QD		
1. I participate in the School Development Planning (eg. Crafting of SIP)	3.62	Very High	3.36	Very High	2.79	High	2.98	High	2.60	High	3.09	High
2. I participate in the regular review of School Improvement Plan to keep it responsive and relevant to emerging needs, challenges and opportunities.	3.62	Very High	3.40	Very High	2.83	High	3.00	High	2.55	High	3.07	High
3. I am involved in the school organization with clear structure and work arrangements that promote shared leadership and governance in accordance with my roles and responsibilities as stakeholder.	3.64	Very High	3.38	Very High	2.86	High	3.10	High	2.73	High	3.14	High

4.	I participate in leadership network facilities communication between and among school and community for informed decision-making and solving of school-community wide learning problems.	3.55	Very High	3.29	High	2.93	High	3.07	High	2.61	High	3.13	High
5.	I participate in the development of a long-term program which operation addresses the training and development needs of school and community leaders.	3.62	Very High	3.36	Very High	2.79	High	3.07	High	2.56	High	3.05	High
Grand Weighted Mean		3.63	Very High	3.36	Very High	2.84	High	3.04	High	2.61	High	3.10	High

Table 2 shows the level of participation of internal stakeholders to the different school-initiated activities in-terms of the leadership and governance.

Results reveal that the School Administrators show the highest level of participation among internal stakeholders with 3.63 grand weighted mean described as **very high**. This implies that School Administrators are the most involved in the school improvement planning, operations and governance of different school activities including organizing, communicating and networking process. The finding is supported by an interview result from one school administrator who stated that, “As a school administrator, I need to assume and model the leading role and responsibility among my stakeholders, thus, I must lead others then for the purpose of implementing various school activities as a direct manager per se, this is the reason why I perceive a *very high* level of participation in my part.”

In contrary, SPGO reflect the **lowest** level of participation with a grand weighted of 2.61. This implies that SPGO has the least involvement in school planning and decision-making activities. The interview results from one SPG Secretary supported this finding, telling that, “As SPG Secretary, I seldom involve in school improvement planning, but my participation to some school activities is in accordance with memorandum or in accomplishment of some project, which is done seldomly.”

General results taken from the five indicators of leadership and governance reveals that internal stakeholders have *high level* of participation with a grand weighted mean of **3.10**, which means that the decentralized decision-making is practiced by the internal stakeholders reflected through *high* participation in the different school-initiated activities. Pañares and Palmes (2014) in their study supported these findings when they mentioned that that school administrators are responsible for the overall operations of school, the one who discovers and take lead on engaging the entire school staff in making decisions that results in more commitment to school reform initiatives.

2. Curriculum and Learning

Table 3
Level of Participation of Internal Stakeholders to Different School-Initiated-Activities in All Elementary schools in San Mariano Districts in Terms of Curriculum and Learning

B. Curriculum and Learning	Internal Stakeholders										Average Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
	School Heads		SBM Coordinators		Teachers' Association		PTA President		SPG Officers			
	WM	QD	WM	QD	WM	QD	WM	QD	WM	QD		
B.1. I participate in seeing to it that the curriculum provides for the development needs of all types of learners in the school community.	3.6	Very High	3.33	Very High	2.76	High	2.71	High	2.54	High	2.99	High
B.2. I participate in the implementation of localized curriculum to make it more meaningful to the learners and applicable to life in the community.	3.55	Very High	3.36	Very High	2.76	High	2.81	High	2.51	High	3.00	High
B.3. I participate in the development of methods and materials for developing creative thinking and problem solving.	3.45	Very High	3.26	High	2.81	High	2.67	High	2.45	High	2.93	High
B.4. I Participate in the regular and collaborative monitoring of learning systems using appropriate tools to ensure the holistic growth and development of the learners	3.5	Very High	3.33	Very High	2.86	High	2.71	High	2.46	High	2.97	High

and the community												
B.5. I participate in the continuous deliberation and review of assessment results using appropriate feedback tools relevant to the learner's local situation and the attainment of relevant life skills.	3.52	Very High	3.31	Very High	2.83	High	2.76	High	2.67	High	3.02	High
B.6. I participate as one among the learning managers and facilitators (teachers, administrators and community members) that nurture values and environments protective of all children and demonstrate behaviors consistent to the organization's vision, mission and goals.	3.45	Very High	3.4	Very High	2.83	High	2.88	High	2.60	High	3.03	High
B.7. I participate in the school advocacy for learner and community-friendly environment, enjoyable, safe, inclusive, accessible and aimed at developing self-directed learners.	3.62	Very High	3.43	Very High	2.95	High	3.05	High	2.76	High	3.16	High
B.8. I participate on school advocacy for learners' essential knowledge, skills, and values to assume	3.6	Very High	3.43	Very High	2.9	High	3	High	2.70	High	3.13	High

responsibility and accountability for their own learning.												
Grand Weighted Mean	3.54	Very High	3.36	Very High	2.84	High	2.82	High	2.59	High	3.03	High

Table 3 shows the level of participation of internal stakeholders to the different school-initiated activities in-terms of the curriculum and learning.

In all the indicators of curriculum and learning, internal stakeholders disclose paralleled results with a grand weighted mean of 3.03 described as *high participation level*. This implies that internal stakeholders are highly involved to the learner’s collaborative development and continuous improvement anchored with the learner’s contexts and aspirations.

In particular, School Administrators got the highest participation level with a very marginal difference to SBM Coordinators as reflected in the grand weighted mean 3.36 to 3.54. Slight differences from the participation level of the other internal stakeholders are seen, except for the SPGO as the lowest with 2.59.

These findings are anchored to the directives of UNESCO’s International Institute for Education Planning (2023) that the development, dissemination and implementation of relevant and effective curriculum and expected learning outcomes that improve teaching and learning is greatly lie on internal stakeholders, the school administrators and teachers in particular.

In an interview conducted, school heads and teachers mentioned that it is their role and responsibility to do continuous curriculum review as to delivery of instructions and assessment in order to make some necessary adjustment to anchor it to the learners’ context and achievement.

3. Accountability and Continuous Improvement

Table 4

Level of Participation of Internal Stakeholders to Different School-Initiated-Activities in All Elementary Schools in San Mariano Districts in Terms of Accountability and Continuous Improvement

C. Accountability and Continuous Improvement	Internal Stakeholders										Average Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
	School Heads		SBM Coordinators		Teachers’ Association		PTA President		SPG Officers			
	WM	QD	WM	QD	WM	QD	WM	QD	WM	QD		
C.1. I participate in defining and agree upon the roles	3.6	Very High	3.36	Very High	2.9	High	2.95	High	2.62	High	3.09	High

and responsibilities of accountable person/s and collective body/ies												
C.2. I participate in the development of performance accountability system in recognizing achievement of goals and assist in addressing them	3.55	Very High	3.26	Very High	2.86	High	2.79	High	2.54	High	3.00	High
C.3. I take part in the formulation of accountability system in the community and its continuous enhancement to ensure that management structures and mechanisms are responsive to the emerging learning needs and demands of the community.	3.52	Very High	3.31	Very High	2.9	High	2.93	High	2.53	High	3.04	High
C.4. I participate in the planning of accountability assessment criteria and tools, feedback mechanisms, and information collection and validation techniques and processes.	3.6	Very High	3.29	Very High	2.83	High	2.93	High	2.56	High	3.04	High
C.5. I participate in the assessment of performance regularly with the community as basis for plan adjustment.	3.6	Very High	3.26	Very High	2.86	High	2.88	High	2.59	High	3.04	High
Grand Weighted Mean	3.57	Very High	3.30	Very High	2.87	High	2.90	High	2.57	High	3.04	High

The level of participation of internal stakeholders to the different school-initiated activities in-terms of the accountability and continuous improvement is disclosed in table 4.

In all the indicators of accountability and continuous improvement, internal stakeholders reveal *high participation level* with grand weighted mean of 3.04. This

implies that internal stakeholders are highly involved to school monitoring and evaluation system on gaps and gains in the implementation of school performance, programs, projects and activities valuing its accountability system.

Specific findings reveal that School Administrators have the highest participation with 3.57 described as very high and the SPGO got the lowest with 2.59 equivalent to high level of participation.

Datnow and Park (2018) supports these findings when he mentioned that continuous improvement and accountability system leverage multiple inputs and processes to achieve desired outcomes without compromising accountability. The efforts to use and review school data for Continuous Improvement often focused to increase accountability demands.

The interview results from a few SGO relates with these findings that when it comes to school prioritization for continuous improvement as per results of monitoring and evaluation on various school activities, school heads and teachers are the most accountable.

These results demand the needs to intensify accountability system of the schools leading to appropriateness of prioritization for continuous improvement.

4. Management of Resources

Table 5

Level of Participation of Internal Stakeholders to Different School-Initiated-Activities in All Elementary Schools in San Mariano Districts in Terms of Management of Resources

D. Management of Resources	Internal Stakeholders										Average Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
	School Heads		SBM Coordinators		Teachers' Association		PTA President		SPG Officers			
	WM	QD	WM	QD	WM	QD	WM	QD	WM	QD		
D.1. I participates in the conduct of regular resource inventory which is collaboratively undertaken by learning managers, learning facilitators, and community stakeholders as basis for resource allocation and mobilization.	3.52	Very High	3.17	Very High	2.74	High	2.67	High	2.47	High	2.91	High
D.2. I participate in a regular dialogue for	3.55	Very High	3.33	Very High	2.71	High	2.86	High	2.46	High	2.98	High

planning and resource programming that is accessible and inclusive, continuously engage and support implementation of community education plans.												
D.3. I participate in the community-developed resource management system that drives appropriate behaviors of the stakeholders to ensure judicious, appropriate, and effective use of resources.	3.6	Very High	3.31	Very High	2.74	High	2.83	High	2.46	High	2.99	High
D.4. I participate in regular monitoring, evaluation, and reporting processes of resource management, collaboratively developed and implemented by the learning managers, facilitators, and community stakeholders.	3.57	Very High	3.33	Very High	2.86	High	2.88	High	2.45	High	3.02	High
D.5. I participate in a system that manages the network and linkages which strengthen and sustain partnerships for improving resource management.	3.6	Very High	3.36	Very High	2.81	High	2.83	High	2.49	High	3.02	High
Grand Weighted Mean	3.57	Very High	3.30	Very High	2.77	High	2.81	High	2.47	Moderate	2.98	High

Table 5 reveals the level of participation of internal stakeholders to the different school-initiated activities in-terms of management of resources.

As per results, the school heads got the highest level of participation with 3.57 grand weighted mean. This implies greater participatory level of school heads in the management of school resources than that of the SPGO who revealed the lowest participation level of 2.47 described as moderate participation.

In general, however, same high participation level is seen in all the dimensions under management of resources from among the internal stakeholders with 2.98 grand weighted mean. This signifies the high participatory level of internal stakeholders to school transparency, effectiveness, and efficiency to support resources towards achieving targeted education outcomes. The same findings revealed in the study of Maritan & Lee (2017). but she emphasized the importance of strategic management of resources. Interview results also supported these findings when the one among the school heads mentioned that the greatest accountability indicated in the roles and responsibilities is the management of resources, where some can be delegated and some cannot.

Table 6 shows the level of participation of external stakeholders to the different school-initiated activities in-terms of the leadership and governance.

External stakeholders reveal an overall *high* level of participation that guaranteed their high involvement in school planning through decision-making. In particular, Barangay Captain perceived the highest participation of 3.37 grand weighted mean with a very marginal difference to Barangay Kagawad who posted 3.24, both described as very high. So far, the lowest is the religious sector with 2.71 grand weighted mean equivalent to *high* level of participation.

These findings revealed in the recommendation of Dela Cruz (2022) in her study that the climate in planning and decision-making in the SBM established deep impact and forged lasting relationships among the constituents that comprise the community – the external stakeholders. The same sounding-lined have mentioned by the Barangay Captain interviewed that both level of awareness and involvement on the school planning and decision-making are usually practiced, especially during the time of crafting and reviewing School Improvement Plan.

These results reveal the needs to intensify school advocacy to sustain or level up external stakeholders' participation to different school-initiated activities as a mean of enhancing SBM level of practice.

b. External Stakeholders
1. Leadership and Governance

Table 6
Level of Participation of External Stakeholders to Different School-Initiated-Activities in All Elementary schools in San Mariano Districts in Terms of Leadership and Governance

A. Leadership and Governance	External Stakeholders						Average Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
	Brgy. Captain		Religious Sector		Brgy. Kagawad			
	WM	QD	WM	QD	WM	QD		
A.1. I participate in the School Development Planning (eg. Crafting of SIP)	3.33	Very High	2.67	High	3.17	High	3.06	High
A.2. I participate in the regular review of School Improvement Plan to keep it responsive and relevant to emerging needs, challenges and opportunities.	3.31	Very High	2.69	High	3.14	High	3.05	High
A.3. I am involved in the school organization with clear structure and work arrangements that promote shared leadership and governance in accordance with my roles and responsibilities as stakeholder.	3.33	Very High	2.81	High	3.36	Very High	3.17	High
A.4. I participate in leadership network facilities communication between and among school and community for informed decision-making and solving of school-community wide learning problems.	3.50	Very High	2.69	High	3.25	Very High	3.15	High
A.5. I participate in the development of a long-term program which operation addresses the training and development needs of school and community leaders.	3.39	Very High	2.69	High	3.28	Very High	3.12	High
Grand Weighted Mean	3.37	Very High	2.71	High	3.24	High	3.11	High

2. Curriculum and Learning

Table 7
Level of Participation of External Stakeholders to Different School-Initiated-Activities in All Elementary schools in San Mariano Districts in Terms of Curriculum and Learning

B. Curriculum and Learning	External Stakeholders						Average Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
	Brgy. Captain		Religious Sector		Brgy. Kagawad			
	WM	QD	WM	QD	WM	QD		
B.1. I participate in seeing to it that the curriculum provides for the development needs of all types of learners in the school community.	3.06	Very High	2.60	High	3.03	High	2.90	High
B.2. I participate in the implementation of localized curriculum to make it more meaningful to the learners and applicable to life in the community.	3.14	Very High	2.71	High	3.17	High	3.01	High

B.3. I participate in the development of methods and materials for developing creative thinking and problem solving.	3.00	Very High	2.62	High	2.86	High	2.83	High
B.4. I Participate in the regular and collaborative monitoring of learning systems using appropriate tools to ensure the holistic growth and development of the learners and the community	3.19	Very High	2.57	High	2.97	High	2.91	High
B.5. I participate in the continuous deliberation and review of assessment results using appropriate feedback tools relevant to the learner's local situation and the attainment of relevant life skills.	3.08	Very High	2.62	High	2.86	High	2.85	High
B.6. I participate as one among the learning managers and facilitators (teachers, administrators and community members) that nurture values and environments protective of all children and demonstrate behaviors consistent to the organization's vision, mission and goals.	3.22	Very High	2.69	High	3.03	High	2.98	High
B.7. I participate in the school advocacy for learner and community-friendly environment, enjoyable, safe, inclusive, accessible and aimed at developing self-directed learners.	3.17	Very High	2.71	High	3.17	High	3.02	High
B.8. I participate on school advocacy for learners' essential knowledge, skills, and values to assume responsibility and accountability for their own learning.	3.14	Very High	2.79	High	3.17	High	3.03	High
Grand Weighted Mean	3.13	High	2.66	High	3.03	High	2.94	High

Table 7 displays the level of participation of external stakeholders to the different school-initiated activities in-terms of the curriculum and learning.

In all the indicators of curriculum and learning, external stakeholders disclose similar results with a grand weighted mean of 2.94 described as *high participation level*. This signifies the high involvement of external stakeholders are to the learner's collaborative development and continuous improvement anchored with the learner's contexts and aspirations.

Specifically, Barangay Captain got the highest participation level with 3.13 grand weighted mean due to their higher position as one among the learning managers and facilitators (community members) that nurture values and environments protective of all children and demonstrate behaviors consistent to the organization's vision, mission and goals which is extremely opposite with the religious sectors, who got the lowest with 2.66.

Cabardo (2016) pointed out that external stakeholders have to enhance their commitment at all levels to their responsibilities and accountabilities in realizing the education outcomes for children congruent to their learning context.

Interview results from religious sector supports these findings when she expressed honestly that their participation to curriculum and learning is not of that expected. This sought to be one among areas for improvement.

These results reveal the school needs to advocate more participation from the external stakeholders, specifically on the dimensions of curriculum and learning.

3. Accountability and Continuous Improvement

Table 8
Level of Participation of External Stakeholders to Different School-Initiated-Activities in All Elementary schools in San Mariano Districts in Terms of Accountability and Continuous Improvement

C. Accountability and Continuous Improvement	External Stakeholders						Average Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
	Brgy. Captain		Religious Sector		Brgy. Kagawad			
	WM	QD	WM	QD	WM	QD		
C.1. I participate in defining and agree upon on the roles and responsibilities of accountable person/s and collective body/ies	3.25	Very High	2.69	High	3.08	High	3.01	High
C.2. I participate in the development of performance accountability system in recognizing achievement of goals and assist in addressing them	3.19	Very High	2.64	High	3.08	High	2.97	High
C.3. I take part in the formulation of accountability system in the community and its continuous enhancement to ensure that management structures and mechanisms are responsive to the emerging learning needs and demands of the community.	3.42	Very High	2.71	High	3.08	High	3.07	High
C.4. I participate in the planning of accountability assessment criteria and tools, feedback mechanisms, and information collection and validation techniques and processes.	3.31	Very High	2.6	High	3.03	High	2.98	High
C.5. I participate in the assessment of performance regularly with the community as basis for plan adjustment.	3.25	Very High	2.6	High	3.06	High	2.97	High
Grand Weighted Mean	3.28	High	2.65	High	3.07	High	3.00	High

The level of participation of external stakeholders to the different school-initiated activities in-terms of the accountability and continuous improvement is disclosed in table 8.

All in all, external stakeholders reveal *high participation level* with grand weighted mean of 3.00 in all the indicators of accountability and continuous improvement. This means that external stakeholders are highly involved to the implementation of school performance, programs, projects and activities valuing its accountability system through school monitoring and evaluation system on gaps and gains.

In particular, Barangay Captains have *very high level of participation* with 3.28 grand weighted mean which is the highest while the Religious sectors is the lowest with 2.65 described as *high*. This emphasizes the higher commitment of Barangay Captain to be involved in the formulation of accountability system and its continuous enhancement within the school and school community, than the religious sectors. Edwards (2013) suggested in his study that primary unit of SBM enhancement relies on the delegation of authority for continuous improvement programs as means to stimulate and sustain development and its accountability. The same idea discloses in an interview from Barangay Captain when he mentioned his vested authority to monitor and evaluate school accomplishment in particular programs, projects and activities delegated upon.

4. Management of Resources

Table 9
Level of Participation of External Stakeholders to Different School-Initiated-Activities in All Elementary schools in San Mariano Districts in Terms of Management of Resources

D. Management of Resources	External Stakeholders						Average Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
	Brgy. Captain		Religious Sector		Brgy. Kagawad			
	WM	QD	WM	QD	WM	QD		
D.1 I participates in the conduct of regular resource inventory which is collaboratively undertaken by learning managers, learning facilitators, and community stakeholders as basis for resource allocation and mobilization.	3.28	Very High	2.57	High	3.03	High	2.96	High
D.2 I participate in a regular dialogue for planning and resource programming that is accessible and inclusive, continuously engage and support implementation of community education plans.	3.36	Very High	2.64	High	3.06	High	3.02	High
D.3 I participate in the community-developed resource management system that drives appropriate behaviors of the stakeholders to ensure judicious, appropriate, and effective use of resources.	3.36	Very High	2.76	High	3.14	High	3.09	High
D.4 I participate in regular monitoring, evaluation, and reporting processes of resource management, collaboratively developed and implemented by the learning managers, facilitators, and community stakeholders.	3.17	High	2.67	High	3.03	High	2.96	High
D.5 I participate in a system that manages the network and linkages which strengthen and sustain partnerships for	3.28	Very High	2.71	High	3.22	High	3.07	High

improving resource management.								
Grand Weighted Mean	3.29	Very High	2.66	High	3.03	High	2.99	High

Table 9 reveals the level of participation of external stakeholders to the different school-initiated activities in-terms of management of resources.

In general, *high* participation level is seen in almost all the dimensions under management of resources from among the external stakeholders except the Brgy Captains whose grand weighted mean is 3.29 and has a *very high* level of participation. This signifies the high involvement of external stakeholders in managing resources. Mojtahedzadeh et. Al. (2013) views in their study negates to this findings when they mentioned that vital to the success of SBM is the accountability to the total performance of the school but will no longer have complete control over its resources. The school heads are most accountable when it comes to management of school resources.

The latter study results support the idea of the interviewed school head when they mentioned that, “delegation of authority can be done to other resources but not in financial matter for it is our sole accountability over the others.”

Table 10

Summary Table in the Level of Participation of Internal and External Stakeholders to the Different School Initiated-Activities in All Elementary Schools of San Mariano I and II Districts

Variables	Internal Stakeholders		External Stakeholders		Mean	Qualitative Description
	Mean	Qualitative Description	Mean	Qualitative Description		
1. Leadership and Governance	3.10	High	3.11	High	3.11	High
2. Curriculum and Learning	3.03	High	2.94	High	2.99	High
3. Accountability and Continuous Improvement	3.04	High	3.00	High	3.02	High
4. Management of Resources	2.98	High	3.02	High	3.00	High

Table 10 summarizes the results of Internal and External Stakeholders Level of Participation to the Different School Initiated-Activities in All Elementary Schools of the two Districts of San Mariano.

Both internal and external stakeholders perceive leadership and governance variate as their highest level of participation with a grand weighted mean of 3.11. This implies that they participated most in the school planning and decision-making or in

leading per se. However, they perceive differently on the variate with lowest participation level. External stakeholders are low in curriculum and learning variate with 2.94 while an emphasis is directed in the results of management of resources variate within the internal stakeholders as the lowest with 2.98. This implies that external stakeholders perceived that they participated higher than the internal stakeholders in the said variate because of their high involvement on the creation of resource management system towards achieving effective use of resources that negates to the idea of school heads in the above-stated interview results as indicated in table 5. On the other hand, external stakeholders are amenable that they participated less in the activities related to curriculum implementation such as instructional delivery and assessment because school heads and teachers have the highest accountability on this variate.

Generally, results reveal that internal and external stakeholders are highly participated in all the indicators within the four SBM principles with very close distinction reflected in each grand weighted mean. Valenzuela (2010) supports these findings when he mentioned that through the initiative of school heads, all elementary schools had successfully introduced and sustained the principles of shared governance and accountability.

2. Result of the Test of Significant Difference in the Level of Participation of Education Stakeholders to Different School-Initiated Activities

a. Internal Stakeholders

Table 11
Result of the Test of Significant Difference in the Level of Participation of Education Stakeholders to Different School-Initiated Activities as Perceived by Internal Stakeholders

Variables	Mean					Probability of <i>f</i>	Remarks
	School Heads	SBM Coordinators	Teachers' Association	PTA President	SPG Officers		
Leadership and Governance	3.63	3.36	2.84	3.04	2.61	0.0056	Significant
Curriculum and Learning	3.54	3.36	2.84	2.82	2.59	0.0017	Significant
Accountability and Continuous Improvement	3.57	3.30	2.87	2.90	2.57	0.0005	Significant
Management of Resources	3.57	3.30	2.77	2.81	2.47	0.0039	Significant

Table 11 discloses the results of the test of the significant difference in the level of participation of internal stakeholders to the different school-initiated activities in-terms of the 4 SBM principles: a) leadership and governance; b) curriculum and learning; c) accountability and continuous improvement; and, d) management of resources.

The results show that the probability of f is less than 0.05 within the four variates. This means the null hypothesis is rejected at 0.05 level of significance, thus, stating that there is significant difference in the level of participation of internal stakeholders to the different school-initiated activities reflected on the slight deviation by the mean in the table along the four (4) variables. The findings of Rutherford (2006) is related to this findings when he stated that in the implementation of SBM, internal stakeholders have new and bigger roles, especially the school heads.

b. External Stakeholders

Table 12

Result of the Test of Significant Difference in the Level of Participation of Education Stakeholders to Different School-Initiated Activities as Perceived by External Stakeholders

Variables	Mean			Probability of f	Remarks
	Barangay Captain	Religious Sector	Barangay Kagawad		
Leadership and Governance	3.37	2.71	3.24	0.0096	Significant
Curriculum and Learning	3.13	2.66	3.03	0.0085	Significant
Accountability and Continuous Improvement	3.28	2.65	3.07	0.0008	Significant
Management of Resources	3.29	2.67	3.10	0.0002	Significant

Table 12 reveals the results of the test of the significant difference in the level of participation of external stakeholders to the different school-initiated activities in-terms of the 4 SBM principles: a) leadership and governance; b) curriculum and learning; c) accountability and continuous improvement; and, d) management of resources.

The results show that the probability of f is less than 0.05 within the four variates which signifies the rejection of the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, results reveal that there is significant difference in the level of participation of external stakeholders to the different school-initiated activities with marginal differences shown in the mean along the four (4) variables.

This idea is supported by Sheldon & Voorhis (2004) when they affirm that community and parental attachment in support to school-based management program can enhance schools and the quality of education through maximum participation on school improvement planning, review and implementation.

c. Internal and External Stakeholders

Table 13

Result of the Test of Significant Difference in the Level of Participation of Education Stakeholders to Different School-Initiated Activities as Perceived by Internal and External Stakeholders

Variables	Mean		Probability of <i>t</i>	Remarks
	Internal Stakeholders	External Stakeholders		
Leadership and Governance	3.10	3.11	0.0447	Significant
Curriculum and Learning	3.03	2.94	0.0245	Significant
Accountability and Continuous Improvement	3.04	3.00	0.0043	Significant
Management of Resources	2.98	3.02	0.0159	Significant

Table 13 presents the results of the test of the significant difference in the level of participation of internal and external stakeholders to the different school-initiated activities in-terms of the 4 SBM principles: a) leadership and governance; b) curriculum and learning; c) accountability and continuous improvement; and, d) management of resources.

The results that reveal the probability of *t* is less than 0.05 within the four variates that implies the rejection of null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance, thus, stating that there is significant difference in the level of participation of internal and external stakeholders to the different school-initiated activities reflected on the very closed differences by the mean in the table along the four (4) variables. This means that internal stakeholders participated higher in the three (3) dimensions, curriculum and learning, accountability and continuous improvement, and management of resources, except in the leadership and governance for external stakeholders is higher. This implies that in the decentralization of authority, the most practiced focus on the planning and decision-making. Dela Cruz (2002) emphasizes these findings when she suggested in her study that the provision of effective leadership will set the pace of all other stakeholders in the community.

3. SBM Level of Practice of All Elementary Schools in San Mariano I & II Districts

Table 14

SBM Level of Practice of All Elementary Schools in San Mariano I & II Districts in-terms of SBM Self-Assessment Using the Revised SBM Self-Assessment Tool

Indicators	Weighted Mean					
	Central	Qualitative Description	Non-Central	Qualitative Description	Integrated	Qualitative Description
A. LEADERSHIP AND GOVERNANCE						
A.1. In place is a Development Plan (e.g., SIP) developed collaboratively by the stakeholders of the school and community	2.50	Advanced	1.92	Maturing	2.79	Advanced
A.2. The development plan (e.g., SIP) is regularly reviewed by the school community to keep it responsive and relevant to emerging needs, challenges and opportunities.	2.00	Maturing	1.81	Maturing	2.43	Maturing
A.3. The school is organized by a clear structure and work arrangements that promote shared leadership and governance and define the roles and responsibilities of the stakeholders.	2.50	Advanced	1.92	Maturing	2.50	Advanced
A.4. A leadership network facilitates communication between and among school and community leaders for informed decision-making and solving of school-community wide learning problems.	2.00	Maturing	1.96	Maturing	2.64	Advanced
A.5. A long-term program is in operation that addresses the training and development needs of school and community leaders.	2.00	Maturing	1.85	Maturing	2.57	Advanced
Grand weighted mean	2.20	Maturing	1.89	Maturing	2.59	Advanced
CURRICULUM AND LEARNING						
B.1. The curriculum provides for the development needs of all types of learners in the school community.	2.50	Advanced	2.23	Maturing	2.50	Advanced
B.2. The implemented curriculum is localized to make it more meaningful to the learners and applicable to life in the community.	2.00	Maturing	2.04	Maturing	2.36	Maturing
B.3. A representative group of school and community stakeholders develop the methods and materials for developing creative thinking and problem solving.	1.50	Maturing	1.92	Maturing	2.29	Maturing
B.4. The learning systems are regularly and collaboratively monitored by the community using appropriate tools to ensure the holistic growth and development of the learners and the community (1)	2.00	Maturing	2.04	Maturing	2.29	Maturing

B.5. The learning systems are regularly and collaboratively monitored by the community using appropriate tools to ensure the holistic growth and development of the learners and the community (2)	2.00	Maturing	1.96	Maturing	2.21	Maturing
B.6. Appropriate assessment tools for teaching and learning are continuously reviewed and improved, and assessment, results are contextualized to the learner and local situation and the attainment of relevant life skills.	1.50	Maturing	2.08	Maturing	2.36	Maturing
B.7. Learning managers and facilitators (teachers, administrators and community members) nurture values and environments that are protective of all children and demonstrate behaviors consistent to the organization's vision, mission and goals. (1)	2.50	Advanced	2.00	Maturing	2.43	Maturing
B.8. Learning managers and facilitators (teachers, administrators and community members) nurture values and environments that are protective of all children and demonstrate behaviors consistent to the organization's vision, mission and goals. (2)	2.50	Advanced	2.12	Maturing	2.50	Advanced
B.9. Methods and resources are learner and community-friendly, enjoyable, safe, inclusive, accessible and aimed at developing self-directed learners. Learners are equipped with essential knowledge, skills, and values to assume responsibility and accountability for their own learning. (1)	2.50	Advanced	1.96	Maturing	2.50	Advanced
B.10. Methods and resources are learner and community-friendly, enjoyable, safe, inclusive, accessible and aimed at developing self-directed learners. Learners are equipped with essential knowledge, skills, and values to assume responsibility and accountability for their own learning. (2)	2.50	Advanced	1.96	Maturing	2.36	Maturing
Grand weighted mean	2.15	Maturing	2.03	Maturing	2.38	Maturing
ACCOUNTABILITY AND CONTINUOUS IMPROVEMENT						
C.1. Roles and responsibilities of accountable person/s and collective body/ies are clearly defined and agreed upon by community stakeholders.	2.50	Advanced	2.00	Maturing	2.36	Maturing
C.2. Achievement of goals is recognized based on a collaboratively developed performance accountability system; gaps are addressed through appropriate action.	2.50	Advanced	2.08	Maturing	2.36	Maturing
C.3. The accountability system is owned by the community and is continuously enhanced to ensure that management structures and mechanisms are responsive to the emerging learning needs and demands of the community.	2.50	Advanced	1.96	Maturing	2.29	Maturing
C.4. Accountability assessment criteria and tools, feedback mechanisms, and information collection and validation techniques and processes are inclusive and collaboratively developed and agreed upon.	2.50	Advanced	2.12	Maturing	2.43	Maturing
C.5. Participatory assessment of performance is done regularly with the community. Assessment results and lessons learned serve as basis for feedback, technical assistance, recognition and plan adjustment.	2.00	Maturing	2.08	Maturing	2.29	Maturing
Grand weighted mean	2.40	Maturing	2.05	Maturing	2.35	Maturing
MANAGEMENT OF RESOURCES						

D.1. Regular resource inventory is collaboratively undertaken by learning managers, learning facilitators, and community stakeholders as basis for resource allocation and mobilization.	2.50	Advanced	2.08	Maturing	2.57	Advanced
D.2. A regular dialogue for planning and resource programming, that is accessible and inclusive, continuously engage stakeholders and support implementation of community education plans.	3.00	Advanced	2.12	Maturing	2.57	Advanced
D.3. In place is a community-developed resource management system that drives appropriate behaviors of the stakeholders to ensure judicious, appropriate, and effective use of resources.	2.00	Maturing	2.00	Maturing	2.43	Maturing
D.4. Regular monitoring, evaluation, and reporting processes of resource management are collaboratively developed and implemented by the learning managers, facilitators, and community stakeholders.	2.00	Maturing	2.04	Maturing	2.50	Advanced
D.5. There is a system that manages the network and linkages which strengthen and sustain partnerships for improving resource management.	2.50	Advanced	2.00	Maturing	2.29	Maturing
Grand weighted mean	2.40	Maturing	2.05	Maturing	2.47	Maturing
OVERALL MEAN	2.29	Maturing	2.00	Maturing	2.45	Maturing

Table 14 displays the SBM Level of Practice of the 42 respondent-schools from San Mariano I and II Districts, 2 Central Schools, 26 Non-Central Schools and 14 Integrated Schools in-terms of four School-Based Management principles: a) leadership and governance; b) curriculum and learning; c) accountability and continuous improvement; and, d) management of resources indicated in the Revised SBM Self-Assessment Tool (RSAT) of DepEd Order No. 83, s. 2012.

The study reveals that integrated schools have an *advanced* SBM Level of practice in-terms of leadership and governance with a grand weighted mean of 2.59, seconded by the Central Schools with 2.20, then the Non-Central Schools with 1.89, described as *maturing* SBM level of Practice. This means that integrated schools, in-terms of leadership and governance exceeded the SBM standard set-forth by the Department of Education. Integrated schools have an advanced practice in school improvement planning, program support and review mechanism and its operational engagement. This finding is similar with the statement of one school administrator from integrated school, stating that, “Based on actual experience, the decentralized decision making is very much practice in our school, from the collaboration in crafting SIP up to its implementation and review. The reason why our school scored *advanced* in-terms of leadership and governance.” However, opposite statements were driven from one school administrator from non-central school, stating that, “During school planning, the conduct of decentralization is somewhat imbalance, on where internal stakeholders do most than the identified external one, thus, I could say that the school fall on maturing level of practice.”

In-terms of curriculum and learning, accountability and continuous improvement and management of resources, all the 42 school-respondents reflected *maturing* SBM Level of practice with grand weighted mean ranging from 1.50 - 2.40. This results significantly reveal the same with the overall mean, 2.29 for Central Schools, 2.00 for

Non-Central Schools and 2.47 for Integrated Schools with a *maturing* qualitative description. This means that the 42 school-respondents are within the standard in-terms of SBM level of practice. It implies that the 42 school-respondents are currently at the level of introducing and sustaining continuous improvement process that integrates wider community participation that improve significant performance and learning outcomes optimum collaboration of the school and the school community as a whole.

Table 15
Summary Table in the SBM Level of Practice of All Elementary Schools in San Mariano I & II Districts

Variables	Mean	Qualitative Description
1. Leadership and Governance	2.23	Maturing
2. Curriculum and Learning	2.19	Maturing
3. Accountability and Continuous Improvement	2.26	Maturing
4. Management of Resources	2.31	Maturing

Table 15 presents the summary table in the SBM level of practice of all elementary schools in San Mariano I & II Districts.

As presented in the table above all elementary schools in San Mariano I and II Districts have *maturing* SBM level of practice which means they complied within the standards set by the Department of Education in-terms of decentralized management as reflected by various indicators per variable.

4. Result of the Test of Significant Difference of SBM Level of Practice

Table 16
Result of the Test of Significant Difference of SBM Level of Practice of Central, Non-Central and Integrated Schools

Variables	Mean			Probability of <i>f</i>	Remarks
	Central	Non-Central	Integrated		
Leadership and Governance	2.20	1.89	2.59	0.1304	Not Significant
Curriculum and Learning	2.15	2.031	2.38	0.5652	Not Significant
Accountability and Continuous Improvement	2.40	2.05	2.35	0.0770	Not Significant
Management of Resources	2.40	2.05	2.47	0.2553	Not Significant

The results of the test of significant difference of SBM level of practice of central, non-central and integrated schools are disclosed in table 16.

It is evident from the results that the probability values of f is greater than 0.05. Therefore, there is no significant difference in the SBM level of practice of central, non-central and integrated schools along the four variables. It shows that the three types of schools do not differ from each other as reflected in their SBM level of practice. It is further inferred that the schools have similarities in their SBM level of practice.

It implies that as per provisions on Operations Manual on School-Based Management and Its Support Systems, 2009, the 42 school-respondents complied within the standard set by the Department of Education, strategically moving forward with common goals: 1) empower the school head to lead their teachers, parents and learners through reforms which lead to higher learning outcomes; 2) bring resources including funds, down to the control of the schools to spur change in line with decentralization; 3) strengthen partnership with all the stakeholders including local government units to invest time, money and effort in making the school a better place to learn; and 4) to institutionalize participatory and knowledge-based continuous school improvement process.

5. Result of the Test of Significant Relationship between the Level of Participation of Education Stakeholders to the SBM level of practice

Table 17
Result of the Test of Significant Relationship Between the Level of Participation of Education Stakeholders to the SBM Level of Practice of All Elementary Schools in San Mariano I & II Districts

Variables	Mean		Significance of r	Remarks
	SBM Level of Practice	Education Stakeholders' Participation		
Leadership and Governance	2.20	3.11	0.0077	Significant
Curriculum and Learning	2.15	2.99	0.0189	Significant
Accountability and Continuous Improvement	2.40	3.02	0.0127	Significant
Management of Resources	2.40	3.00	0.0127	Significant

Table 17 presents the results of the test of significant relationship between the level of participation of education stakeholders to the SBM level of practice of all elementary schools in San Mariano I and II Districts.

The results reveal that the probability values of r is lesser than 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at 0.05 level of significance. Thus, there is significant relationship between the level of participation of education stakeholders to the SBM level of practice of all elementary schools in San Mariano I and II Districts. It shows that the level of participation of education stakeholders does affect the SBM level of practice of all elementary schools in the two districts of San Mariano.

The study of Varatharaj (2015) supported this findings when he discloses the same that SBM is an adaptation made to improve the education system that gives the school autonomy of decision-making on administration and management through decentralization of authority among education stakeholders.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of this study, the level of participation of internal and external stakeholders in the different school-initiated activities in the two (2) districts of San Mariano is high. In Particular, school heads reveal the highest participation within the internal stakeholders and SPGO has the lowest. Among the external stakeholders, Barangay Captains perceive the highest level of participation and religious sectors are the lowest. This implies that the stakeholders who got the highest participation level are the most involved in all the dimensions within SBM parameters.

Hypothetically, it is concluded that there is a significant difference in the level of participation of internal and external stakeholders to the different school-initiated activities. This implies the varying extent of participation among them as reflected on the marginal difference in the mean per variate. However, there is no significant difference in the SBM level of practice Central, Non-Central and Integrated Schools in San Mariano I and Districts which disclosed the acceptance of the null hypothesis along the four variables.

Another, though integrated schools captured an advanced SBM level of practice in-terms of leadership and governance, the general findings still prevail that the three types of schools got a maturing SBM level of practice within the four (4) variates. Therefore, similarities among the three (3) types of schools are noted in-terms of SBM level of practice.

Generally, it is therefore concluded that the higher level of participation of education stakeholders to the different school-initiated activities, particularly on the indicators relative to the principles of SBM, which are the variables of the study, the greater is probability to enhance or to achieve an advanced SBM level of practice of the schools.

Recommendations

Relative to the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are offered as inputs for an improved school-based management implementation.

1. The school must have functional SPT to device an appropriate mechanism through advocacy system to level up and encourage maximum participation among internal and external stakeholders towards enhancement of shared responsibilities and governance.

2. Empowerment of the SPT must be intensified particularly in their roles and responsibilities in the school and school community.
3. The school should establish a reward system to encourage maximum participation among internal and external stakeholders as means to further enhance their SBM level of practice.
4. The SPT must act as the leader, to model maximum participation in the implementation of the different school-initiated activities through the decentralized leadership of its internal and external stakeholders.
5. Stakeholders involvement in the enhancement of SBM level of practice should be further improved. The sense of shared responsibility should be inculcated among stakeholders through modelling shared governance and transparency.
6. Integrated Schools Administrators should mentor Central and Non-Central Schools particularly in the leadership and governance roles. There must be a mentoring program for school heads and so with the SPT.
7. The school should develop and intensify the implementation of sustainable communication plan to further disseminate and fast-track the delivery of information and updates among stakeholders as early mechanism to enhance participation.
8. The school must develop a sustainable mechanism to regularly track the participation level of stakeholders to the school-initiated activities as basis for making plan adjustments and interventions.
9. The conduct of similar or related researches should be further recommended as follows:
 - a. Factors Affecting the SBM Level of Practice Implementation in All Secondary Schools;
 - b. Education Stakeholders' Challenges and Coping Mechanism to Enhance Participation Level to SBM Related Activities;
 - c. Impact of SBM Strategic Interventions: An Aid to Enhance SBM level of Practices in All Public Elementary Schools

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher made sure that during the conduct of the study, the following ethical concerns were followed to necessitate safe, anti-fraud, deliberate, and careful undertakings in the study:

1. The researcher, through proper communications, asked permission from the Division Office, and other concerned offices for the study;
2. The researcher also acknowledged the Department of Education and the Schools Division of Isabela for allowing her to conduct the study;
3. The researcher informed the respondents of the study through letters and a short orientation to the study. Data and information gathered were treated with utmost respect and confidentiality;
4. The researcher, properly cited gathered information and other relevant studies from authors, books, or any publications through proper citation.

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REFERENCES

- Cabardo, J. R. (2016). Level of participation of the school stakeholders to the different school-initiated activities and the implementation of school-based management. *Journal of Inquiry & Action in Education*. Retrieved from https://issuu.com/internationalresearch8/docs/best_practices_in_brigada_eskwela_of_secondary_sch
- Curriculum and expected learning outcomes. (2023). Retrieved from <https://learningportal.iiep.unesco.org/en/issue-briefs/improve-learning/curriculum-and-expected-learning-outcomes>
- Datnow, A., & Park, V. (2018). Opening or closing doors for students? Equity and data use in schools. *Journal of Educational Change**. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10833-018-9323-6>
- Dela Cruz, R. (2022). Stakeholders' participation in the school-based management in the public elementary school in San Pablo City, Philippines. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/365025008_Stakeholders'_Participation_in_School-Based_Management_of_a_Public_Elementary_School_in_San_Pablo_City_Philippines
- Edwards, V. (2013). A theory of participation in the 21st century governance. *International Journal of Organization Theory and Behavior*. <https://doi.org/1108/IJOTB-16-01-2013-B001>

- Maritan, C. A., & Lee, G. K. (2017). Resource allocation and strategy. *Journal of Management*, 43(8), 2411-2420. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0149206317729738>
- Mojtahedzadeh, et al. (2013). The role of school-based management in developing countries. *Global Journal of Biodiversity Science and Management*. Retrieved from <https://policytoolbox.iiep.unesco.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/09/Full-Bibliography-Formatted-ongoing-1.xlsx>
- Pañares, N., & Palmes, N. (2014). School-based management (SBM) implementation in the school divisions of Misamis Oriental: An assessment for policy recommendation. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.10750.48966>
- Rutherford, D. (2006). Setting up the school partnership: Some insights from Birmingham's Collegiate Academies. *School Leadership and Management*. Retrieved from <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ753578>
- Sheldon, S. B., & Van Voorhis, V. L. (2004). Partnership programs in US schools: Their development and relationship to family involvement outcomes. *School Effectiveness and School Improvement*. <https://doi.org/10.1076/sesi.15.2.125.30434>
- UNESCO's International Institute for Education Planning. (2023). Curriculum and expected learning outcomes. <https://learningportal.iiep.unesco.org/en/issue-briefs/improve-learning/curriculum-and-expected-learning-outcomes>
- Valenzuela, E. A. P. (2010). Decentralization of education in the Philippines. Retrieved from https://gseuphsdlibrary.files.wordpress.com/2013/03/decentralization_education_philippines.pdf
- Varatharaj, R., Abdullah, A. G. K., & Ismail, A. (2015). The effect of teacher autonomy on assessment practices among Malaysian cluster school teachers. *International Journal of Asian Social Science*. Retrieved from <https://archive.aessweb.com/index.php/5007/article/view/2713>